

Zinner's Syndrome: Report of two cases with different symptoms managed by minimally invasive approach

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ABSTRACT Background: Zinner's syndrome is characterized by triad of seminal vesicle cysts with ipsilateral renal agenesis and ejaculatory duct obstruction. It sometimes becomes symptomatic during reproductive time of the patient. In this article, we present a minimally invasive approach for two patients with Zinner syndrome.

Case presentation: First patient was 37 years old man with 5 years history of infertility. Semen analysis was typical for obstructive azoospermia and ultrasonography revealed the absence of left kidney and anechoic pelvic mass with a thick wall. MRI confirmed Zinner's syndrome showing 9 cm sized seminal vesicle cyst on the posterior of the bladder. The second patient was 18 years old boy with one year history of abdominal-pelvic pain and lower urinary tract symptoms. Ultrasonography revealed the absence of right kidney and fluid-filled cystic lesion behind the bladder. Contrast enhanced CT confirmed Zinner's syndrome diagnosis showing solitary left kidney with 8 cm sized seminal vesicle cyst on the posterior of the bladder. We performed laparoscopic seminal vesicle cyst excision for both patient successfully. The procedure was performed with transperitoneal access using four trocars for two patients.

Conclusions: Laparoscopic approach for seminal vesicle cysts is feasible because it provides quicker recovery and less morbidity. Therefore it should be considered for treating seminal vesicle cysts.

KEYWORDS Zinner Syndrome's, Seminal vesicle cyst, laparoscopy

Introduction

Zinner Syndrome first described by Zinner is a rare triad of renal agenesis, ipsilateral seminal vesical cyst and ejaculatory duct obstruction. It is a developmental arrest during embryogenesis between 4. and 13. weeks affecting the caudal end of the mullerian duct [1]. Less than 300 cases were reported so far. Although the syndrome can present with different symptoms, these patients are usually diagnosed by insidently and remain asymptomatic. During reproductive time of the patient the syndrome becomes symptomatic between 2nd and 4th decades. These symptoms can be lower urinary tract symptoms, dysuria, pelvic and per-

ineal pain, hematospermy, painful ejaculation and infertility. Herein, we present two cases of Zinner's Syndrome with different symptoms. Both of them were treated successfully by the removal of the mass seminal vesical cysts with laparoscopy in surgery.

Case report

Case 1

The first patient was 37 years old who was married for 7 years and attempted to have a baby for 5 years. He presented with abdominal pain and painful ejaculation. In his physical examination there was no palpable mass. His left testis was undescended. His semen analysis was azoospermia with low semen volume and acidic pH which was typical for obstructive azoospermia. His native blood tests and urine analyses were normal. And there was no any other remarkable finding in his physical examination or blood tests. Ultrasonography revealed absence of left kidney and anechoic pelvic mass with a thick wall. In contrast enhanced MRI we found 90x75x70 mm sized solid mass on the posterior of the bladder and there was an atrophic

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Figure 1

Axial MRI image shows single right kidney(A).T1-weighted MRI shows left seminal vesicle cyst with coronal(B), sagittal(C) and axial(D) demonstrations.

testicle with ovoid form anterior of the external iliac chain.

Case 2

The second patient was 18 year old young boy who was suffering from abdominal-pelvic pain and voiding problems for one year. His physical examination, routine blood tests and urinalysis were normal. Ultrasonography revealed the absence of right kidney and fluid-filled cystic lesion behind the bladder. In contrast enhanced CT we found left solitary kidney and a 78x67 mm sized seminal vesical cyst on the posterior of the bladder arising from seminal vesicle.

Based on the all findings a diagnosis of Zinner's syndrome was determined for the patients. We have performed laparoscopic left orchiectomy and seminal vesicle cyst excision for the first patient and for second patient laparoscopic seminal vesicle cyst excision was carried out.The pathology was epidermal type keratinous cyst for first patient and squamous metaplasia for second patient. Cystoscopy was performed for both patients before the removal of cyst and during cystoscopy ureteral orifice wasn't found with the same side of absent kidney.

For the procedure, the patients were placed in the Trendelenburg position and a transperitoneal approach with four ports were used similar to radical prostatectomy. After the insufflation rectovesical peritoneum was incised and seminal vesicle, vas deferens and the cyst were identified. Seminal vesicle cyst dissected carefully and aspirated it's fluid. After the complete dissection of the cyst it was placed into an endobag. One drain was put at the end of the operation. There were minimal loss of blood for our patients. There were no intraoperative and postoperative complications for both operations. The patients were discharged 3 days after the operation.

Discussion

Zinner Syndrome is a triad of renal agenesis,ipsilateral seminal vesicle cyst and ejaculatory duct obstruction which first reported in 1914 by Zinner. An understanding of the embryology and anatomy of genitourinary tract is essential to make accurate diagnosis of developmental anomalies of the genitourinary tract

Figure 2

Contrast-enhanced axial CT of the abdomen shows solitary left kidney(a).Contrast-enhanced CT demonstrates cystic lesion in the region of right seminal vesicle with coronal(b),sagittal(c) and axial(d) reconstructions.The cyst doesn't show any enhancement.

[1]. Kidney and seminal vesicle cysts have common embryological origin. The ureteral bud originates from distal mesonephric duct and induce differentiation of the metanephric blastem. The mesonephric duct differentiations into the appendix of epididymis, paradidymis, epididymis, vas deferens, ejaculatory duct, seminal vesicle and hemitrigone. Malfunction of mesonephric duct results absence of ipsilateral kidney, ureter, hemitrigone while seminal vesicle is preserved [1].

Less than 5 cm seminal vesicle cysts generally stay asymptomatic and can be found incidentally. But larger cysts (>8-10 cm) are usually symptomatic. Pressure of the seminal vesicle cyst to the organs beside it presents the symptoms. Abdominal, pelvic and perineal pain are very common. Dysuria, polyuria, painful ejaculation, hematuria, urinary tract infections, epididymitis and prostatitis can be seen [2]. Larger than 12 cm cysts are known as giant cysts. These can result bladder and colonic obstruction [2, 3]. Various image techniques enable to determine this rare anomaly. Such as USG, CT, MRI and vasovesiculography. On sonography absence of ipsilateral kidney, obstructed ejaculatory ducts can be found. However USG is sometimes unable to visualise the cyst posterior of the bladder. However, still, it's the first-line imaging technique because of cheapness and easy accessibility. On CT mass retrovesicular periprostatic cyst with absence of ipsilateral renal agenesis can be seen [4]. MRI is the best image technique for understanding mesonephric duct anomalies and being able to differentiate the seminal vesicle cysts from other cystic pelvic masses. MRI is superior to CT as it demonstrates the anatomy of pelvis and can identify the ectopic ureter orifices which are missed on CT [5]. Although MRI has superiority to CT, diagnosis of Zinner Syndrome was very clear for second patient so we didn't need further evaluation. We can also use vasovesiculography to confirm this syndrome by injecting contrast material into the vas deferens ducts to visualise seminal vesicle. Due to ejaculatory duct obstruction reflux of contrast from dilated seminal vesicle to ipsilateral atretic ureter is seen in

Zinner Syndrome [5]. We opted not to utilise this type of image technique due to its invasiveness. For our two patients CT and MRI was enough to confirm diagnosis after USG findings.

Decision of treatment depends on cyst's size, patient's symptoms and its severity. Small and asymptomatic cysts can be followed with medical treatment or no intervening [6].

But symptomatic and larger cysts can be treated with percutaneous drainage or transurethral/transrectal aspiration, transurethral resection of ejaculatory duct (TUR-ED), open surgery and minimal invasive techniques such as laparoscopic or robotic surgery. Due to high risk of recurrence, percutaneous drainage or transurethral/transrectal aspiration are not recommended [7]. Although open surgery has great effectiveness for treating pelvic cysts but we didn't prefer it because of its higher morbidity and risk of complication such as bladder, rectal, ureteral injuries, pelvic urinoma and erectile dysfunction. Minimally invasive approach is becoming gold standard treatment day by day for treating Zinner's Syndrome. Since Kavoussi et al. described using laparoscopy for retrovesical lesions it became preferred method for treating such patients [8]. Because minimally invasive approach provides perfect visualization during operation, less morbidity and faster recovery than open surgery. It also allows to see other accompanying anatomic malformities such as undescended testicle as in our case or ectopic ureter insertion, ectopic vasa deferentia insertion and bilateral seminal vesicle cyst involvement [9]. So far robot-assisted laparoscopic surgery is becoming another favorable minimally invasive technique and also for accompanying malformities. It also can be used when it is possible [10].

Conclusion

Today minimally invasive approach's superiority to open surgery is obvious for treating seminal vesicle cysts. Laparoscopy is considered to be one of the minimally invasive tool in our disposal. A successful laparoscopic treatment can provide better recovery and less morbidity as in our two patients.

Competing Interests

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